

Mapping Survey Questions to Research Questions

The following table presents the survey items administered to students, along with the research question(s) each item was designed to inform.

Question #	Survey Question	Related RQ(s)
1	Did you understand the modelling as a virtual graph of optimisation problems for the subsequent application of the generic and reusable A* algorithm provided in the course?	RQ1.1
2	Do you consider that the proposed method facilitates the application of the A* algorithm to optimisation problems?	RQ2.1
3	Were you able to apply the A* algorithm using the presented approach in optimisation problems?	RQ1.1
4	Was it clear to you how to transform an optimisation problem into a virtual graph using the approach presented?	RQ1.1
5	Were you able to properly design the nodes and edges during the modelling of the problem as a virtual graph in the given exercises?	RQ1.1
6	Do you find that modelling problems as virtual graphs facilitates the reasoning that has to be carried out to solve different optimisation problems?	RQ1.1, RQ2.1
7	Do you consider that the visualisation provided by the software improved your understanding of the results of the A* algorithm in the given exercises?	RQ1.2, RQ3.2
8	Did the software provided allow you to quickly identify the optimal path in the given exercises?	RQ1.2, RQ2.2, RQ3.2
9	Did the software provided allow you to quickly identify other relevant results in the given exercises?	RQ1.2, RQ2.2, RQ3.2
10	Compared to the manual implementation of Algorithm A*, do you prefer to use the provided software to solve optimisation problems?	RQ2.1, RQ3.1
11	Do you consider the proposed approach to be simpler than traditional approaches when it comes to solving any optimisation problem?	RQ2.1, RQ3.1
12	Do you think that the combination of theoretical teaching and the software tool enhanced your learning experience?	RQ3.1
13	Do you feel more confident in applying the A* algorithm after learning with this approach?	RQ3.1
14	Do you think you could use this approach to tackle optimisation problems in real-world situations?	RQ2.1